

Impact of *Coelaenomenodera lameensis* (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae : Hispinae) on the Production of Oil palm Plantations at Different Age Groups

Author's Details:

Ahou Cyprienne KOUASSI^{1,2*}, Akpa Alexandre Moïse AKPESSÉ¹, N'klo HALA², Assienin Hauverset N'GUESSAN², Kouakou Hervé KOUA¹, Kouassi Philippe KOUASSI¹

¹University Félix Houphouët-Boigny, UFR Biosciences, Laboratory of Natural Environment and Biodiversity Conservation, Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire, 22 BP 582 Abidjan 22 Côte d'Ivoire

²National Agronomic Research Center (La Mé Station), 13 BP 989 Abidjan 13 Côte d'Ivoire

*Corresponding Author: Tel : + 225 0709763064/ Email: ahoucypr@gmail.com

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Abstract

Coelaenomenodera lameensis is an oil palm leaf miner. This insect pest causes extensive damage to palm trees in production. To take good measures to protect palm trees against this pest, it is important to know beforehand, its real impact on production. For this, a study was carried out over 5 consecutive years (January 2015 to December 2019) on production plots of the La Mé station of the National Agronomic Research Center. These plots, with an area of between 1 and 3 ha, were divided into 4 categories according to age (8 to 20 years old; 21 to 35 years old; 36 to 50 years old; 51 to 64 years old). In each age group, 10 plots were chosen and monthly surveys of the population level of *C. lameensis* were carried out on each plot. At the same time, the number of bunches of oil palm harvested each month on each plot was carefully recorded from the harvest records. The study showed that an increase in the population level of *C. lameensis* leads to a decrease in production and inversely. Indeed, strong significant negative correlations were observed between the population level of *C. lameensis* and production. Also, the drops in production were smaller on the oldest plots (51 to 64 years old). In addition, the population level of *C. lameensis* and production decrease with increasing age of plots. Thus, the highest population level of *C. lameensis* and the highest production were recorded on the youngest plots (8 to 20 years). Monitoring of palm groves should be regular, especially at a young age in order to avoid, on the one hand, production losses and, on the other hand, to better forecast the periods of decline and increase in production relative to the age of palms.

Keywords : Oil palm, *Coelaenomenodera lameensis*, Production, age group, plots, correlation

INTRODUCTION

The oil palm is the primary source of fatty substances in the world (USDA, 2015). The oils extracted from this plant, palm oil and palm kernel oil are essential in many culinary preparations today. They are also used in the manufacture of many agrifood, cosmetic and biofuel products (Ataga and Van der vossen, 2007). However, its culture is confronted with the attacks of many defoliating insects including *C. lameensis* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae, Hispinae). Indeed, *C. lameensis* is an oil palm leaf miner and is the main pest of oil palm in West Africa and, in particular, in Côte d'Ivoire (Mariau *et al.*, 1981; Mariau, 2001; Koua, 2008; Koua *et al.*, 2010; Coffi *et al.*, 2012). The damage is caused by both adults and larvae. The adults progressively feed on the leaflets of low palms to those of tall palms (Mariau, 2001; Tano *et al.*, 2013). They groove 12 to 15 mm across the entire thickness of the leaflet from the underside and in large numbers can cause partial or even complete drying out of the palms. The leaf miner larvae are by far the most dangerous. They burrow in the lamina of the leaflets to feed. These galleries enlarge with the larval stages and during the period of proliferation, one can count several thousand larvae per leaf. This causes the direct destruction and almost total drying out of the palm (Mariau and Besombes, 1972) and the palm grove appears to be devastated by a fire (Morin and Mariau, 1971). Previous studies have shown that the damage caused by this pest can cause a drop in production of up to 30 to 50% over a period of 2 to 3 years (Mariau, 2001). Given the important role played by the oil palm, it seems necessary at the present time to know the real impact of

this pest on the production of this plant. This will make it possible, on the one hand, to better control the populations of this pest and, on the other hand, to take good measures to avoid possible production losses.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study site

The experiment was carried out at the experimental station of the National Agronomic Research Center (CNRA) of La Mé (5 °26'LN, 3 °50'W) located in the South-Eastern of Côte d'Ivoire. The climate is equatorial type of transition (Péné and Assa, 2003) characterized by 4 seasons of unequal duration including two distinct rainy seasons. The long rainy season lasts from April to July and the short rainy season from October to November. These alternate with two dry seasons. A large one that runs from December to March and a small one from August to September. This climate is generally consistent with that of the forested Ivory Coast, favorable to the cultivation of oil palm.

Experimentations

The study was carried out from January 2015 to December 2019 on plots in production at the La Mé station of the National Agronomic Research Center. The age of the plots was between 8 and 64 years old, divided into 4 groups (8 to 20 years old; 21 to 35 years old; 36 to 50 years old; 51 to 64 years old). In each age group, 10 plots were chosen. The area of the plots was between 1 and 3 ha. It was a question of showing the influence of the damage of *C. lameensis* on the oil palm production of these plots. Thus, phytosanitary surveys covering populations of *C. lameensis* larvae and adults (Figure 1) were carried out each month on each plot. The readings were taken every 2 lines on each plot. On each row, 12 trees were chosen (4 trees in the North, 4 trees in the Center and 4 trees in the South) and 4 palms are observed at the level of each tree. At the same time, the palms are lowered one after the other using a fork. External adults of *C. lameensis* on the leaflets of lowered palms are first counted to prevent them from blowing away. Subsequently, the larval galleries on the leaflets are opened using forceps and the larvae are then counted. Also, the number of bunches of oil palm harvested each month on each plot was carefully recorded from the harvest records. In addition, the number of bunches harvested in one year was compared with that of the following year to determine losses. Thus, we evaluated :

- The average index of larvae (Iml): $Iml = \Sigma (La/np)$
with La: Number of larvae, Np: Number of palms checked
- The average index of adults (Imad): $Imad = \Sigma (ad/np)$
with ad: Number of adults, np: Number of palms checked
- The total number of bunches harvested (NTr): $NTr = (\Sigma_1^n(Nr))$
with Nr: Number of bunches obtained during each harvest period
- Production losses (PPro): $PPro: \Sigma (Nra-Nrs)/na$
with Nra: Number of bunches harvested during the previous year, Nrs: Number of bunches harvested during the following year (year when there is a drop in production) and na: Number of years

October 31, 2021

Figure 1: Some stages of *C. lameensis* development

a: Larva at stage 4, **b:** Adult

Statistical analysis of data

Pearson's correlation test is a test that measures the relationship between 2 variables with a normal distribution. This test was established using Statistica software version 7.1 to determine the relationship between the mean index of *C. lameensis* and the production of oil palm. An analysis of variance (ANOVA 1) was carried out using the same software to determine the plots on which the production losses were higher or lower. Means were graded using Duncan's Test at the 5% level.

RESULTS

Influence of average index of *C. lameensis* larvae on the production

From this study, it emerges overall that the increase in oil palm production is the result of a decrease in the average index of *C. lameensis* larvae and inversely.

On the 8 to 20 years old plots, the average larval index fell from 2015 to 2016 and from 2017 to 2018 as the number of bunches increased. Thus, the average larval index of *C. lameensis* went from 3.33 (2015) to 1.91 larva/palm in 2016 and from 2.58 (2017) to 0.88 larva/palm in 2018. Similarly, production increased from 8905 (2015) to 42422 bunches in 2016 and from 15802 (2017) to 58522 bunches in 2018. On the other hand, the average larval index has increased (from 2016 to 2017 and from 2018 to 2019) followed by a drop in production. In fact, the average larvae index went from 1.91 (2016) to 2.58 larvae/palm (2017) and from 0.88 to 1.38 larva/palm (2019) with a production varying from 42422 (2016) to 15802 bunches in 2017 and from 58522 (2018) to 38755 bunches in 2019 (Figure 2a).

Regarding plots from 21 to 35 years old, the study revealed a drop in the average number of *C. lameensis* larvae from 2015 to 2016 and from 2017 to 2018. During these different periods, we also observed, an increase in production. Thus, the average index of *C. lameensis* larvae went from 2.88 (2015) to 0.95 adult/palm in 2016 and from 1.97 (2017) to 0.58 adult/palm in 2018. Similarly, production increased from 7148 (2015) to 38101 bunches in 2016 and from 12482 (2017) to 55522 bunches in 2018. Also, an increase in the average index of *C. lameensis* larvae was observed from 2016 to 2017 and from 2018 to 2019, in contrast to the production which suffered a decrease. The average larvae index thus went from 0.95 larva/palm (2016) to 1.97 larva/palm in 2017 and from 0.58 (2018) to 0.78 larva/palm in 2019. As for production, it went from 38101 (2016) to 12482 bunches in 2017 and from 55522 (2018) to 35424 bunches in 2019 (Figure 2b).

On the 36-50 years old plots, the average larvae count declined from 2015 to 2016 and 2017 to 2018 as the number of bunches increased. The average larvae index thus varied from 0.44 (2015) to 0.07 larva/palm

October 31, 2021

in 2016 and from 0.43 larva/palm (2017) to 0.05 larva/palm in 2018. The production is then increased from 6228 (2015) to 28548 bunches in 2016 and from 8502 (2017) to 38705 bunches in 2018.

In addition, an increase in the population level of *C. lameensis* larvae was observed from 2016 to 2017 and from 2018 to 2019 as production declined. Thus, the average larval index fluctuated from 0.07 larva/palm in 2016 to 0.43 larva/palm in 2017 and from 0.05 (2018) to 0.41 larva/palm in 2019. The production is then increased from 28548 (2016) to 8502 regimes in 2017 and from 38705 (2018) to 20982 bunches in 2019 (Figure 2c).

At the 51-64 years old plots, the average number of *C. lameensis* larvae decreases from 2015 to 2016 and from 2017 to 2018 as production increases. The average index of *C. lameensis* larvae thus increased from 1 (2015) to 0.05 larva/palm in 2016 and from 0.8 (2017) to 0.04 larva/palm in 2018. As for production, it increased from 5433 (2015) to 25982 bunches in 2016 and from 5702 (2017) to 30753 bunches in 2018. The larval population level also increased from 2016 to 2017 and from 2017 to 2018. This increase in larval population level is accompanied by a decline in production. Indeed, the average larval index went from 0.05 (2016) to 0.8 larva/palm in 2017 and from 0.04 (2018) to 0.8 larva/palm in 2019. Similarly, production increased from 25982 (2016) to 5702 bunches in 2017 and from 30753 (2018) to 15382 bunches in 2019 (Figure 2d).

Figure 2 : Evolution of production as a function of the average index of *C. lameensis* larvae on the plots prospected

a : Plots of de 8 to 20 years old, **b :** Plots of 21 to 35 years old,

c : Plots of 36 to 50 years old, **d :** Plots of 51 to 64 years old

Correlation between the average index of *C. lameensis* larvae and the production

October 31, 2021

On all the categories of plots, a significant negative correlation ($P < 0.05$) was observed between the average number of larvae and the number of bunches with, $Y = 73197.98 - 19998.4 x$ and $r = - 0.95$ at the level of plots of 8 to 20 years, $Y = 56973.84 - 19,021.26 x$ and $r = - 0.93$ at the level of plots of 21 to 35 years, $Y = 37700.29 - 61097.47 x$ and $r = - 0.9$ at the level of plots of 36 to 50 years and $Y = 29482.07 - 23850.68 x$ and $r = - 0.94$ at the level of plots of 51 to 60 years (Figure 3).

October 31, 2021

d

Figure 3: Linear correlation between production and average *C. lameensis* larvae index on the plots prospected

a : Plots of 8 to 20 years old, b : Plots of 21 to 35 years old, c : Plots of 36 to 50 years old,
d : Plots of 51 to 64 years old

Influence of average index of *C. lameensis* adults on the production

The study showed that as the average adult index of *C. lameensis* increases, the number of bunches harvested decreases and inversely. This change in the average index of *C. lameensis* adults and production was observed on all the plots surveyed.

On the 8 to 20 years old plots, the average index of *C. lameensis* adult fell from 2015 to 2016 and from 2017 to 2018 while during these periods the number of bunches increased. The average index of *C. lameensis* adults thus went from 4.22 (2015) to 1.91 adult/palm in 2016, from 2.98 (2017) to 0.88 adult/palm in 2018. Similarly, production increased from 8905 (2015) to 42422 bunches in 2016 and from 15802 (2017) to 58522 bunches in 2018. Conversely, the average index of adults increased from 2016 to 2017 and from 2018 to 2019 while that production suffered a decline. The average index of adults then fell from 1.91 (2016) to 2.98 adults/palm in 2017 and from 0.88 (2018) to 1.38 adult/palm in 2019. Production also increased from 42422 (2016) to 15802 bunches in 2017 and from 58522 (2018) to 38755 bunches in 2019 (Figure 4a).

On plots aged 21 to 35, the average index of *C. lameensis* adults declined from 2015 to 2016 and from 2017 to 2018 as the number of bunches increased. Thus, the average index of *C. lameensis* adults went from 4.02 (2015) to 1.18 adult/palm in 2016 and from 2.98 (2017) to 0.86 adult/palm in 2018. From Likewise, production increased from 7148 (2015) to 38101 bunches in 2016 and from 12482 (2017) to 55522 bunches in 2018. In addition, the average index of *C. lameensis* adults increased from 2016 to 2017 and from 2018 to 2019 when production suffered a decline during this period. The average adults index then went from 1.18 (2016) to 2.98 adults/palm in 2017 and from 0.86 in 2018 to 0.98 adults/palm in 2019. As for production, it went from 38,101 (2016) to 12482 plans in 2017 and from 55522 (2018) to 35424 plans in 2019 (Figure 4b).

At the 36 to 50 years old plots level, the average index of *C. lameensis* adults decreases from 2015 to 2016 and from 2017 to 2018 as the number of bunches increases. Thus, the average adult index of *C. lameensis* went from 2 (2015) to 0.02 adult/palm in 2016 and from 1.85 (2017) to 0.11 adult/palm in 2018. The production is then increased from 6228 (2015) to 28548 bunches in 2016 and from 8502 (2017) to 38705 bunches in 2018.

In addition, the adult population level of *C. lameensis* increased from 2016 to 2017 and from 2018 to 2019 as production declined. Thus, the average index of *C. lameensis* adults went from 0.02 (2016) to 1.85 adult/palm in 2017 and from 0.11 (2018) to 1.5 adult/palm in 2019. The production increased from 28548 (2016) to 8502 bunches in 2017 and from 38705 (2018) to 20982 bunches in 2019 (Figure 4c).

At the 51-64 years old plots level, when the average index of *C. lameensis* adult decreases (from 2015 to 2016 and from 2017 to 2018), the number of bunches increases. Thus, the average index of *C. lameensis* adults went from 1.98 (2015) to 0.03 adult/palm in 2016 and from 1.5 (2017) to 0.04 adult/palm in 2018. The production then increased from 5433 (2015) to 25982 bunches in 2016 and from 5702 (2017) to 30753

October 31, 2021

bunches in 2018. The adult population level also increased from 2016 to 2017 and 2018 to 2019, while production declined during these different periods. The adult population level thus fluctuated from 0.03 (2016) to 1.5 adult/palm in 2017 and from 0.04 (2018) to 1.7 adult/palm in 2019. As for production, it increased from 25982 (2016) to 5702 regimes in 2017 and from 30753 (2018) to 15382 regimes in 2019 (Figure 4d).

Figure 4: Evolution of production as a function of the average index of adults of *C. lameensis* on the plots prospected

a : Plots of 8 to 20 years old, b : Plots of 21 to 35 years old,

c : Plots of 36 to 50 years old, d : Plots of 51 to 64 years old

Correlation between the average index of adults of *C. lameensis* and the production

A strong and significant negative correlation ($P < 0.05$) was observed between the mean index of *C. lameensis* adults and the number of bunches on all the plots prospected with $Y = 65650.40 - 144193.38 x$ and $r = - 0.95$ at the level of plots from 8 to 20 years old, $Y = 55763.31 - 12987.98 x$ and $r = - 0.93$ at the level of plots from 21 to 35 years old, $Y = 35001.12 - 3146.1 x$ and $r = - 0.92$ at the 36-50 years old plots and $Y = 28463.87 - 11250.93 x$; $r = - 0.92$ at the level of plots aged 51 to 64 (Figure 5).

October 31, 2021

Figure 5: Linear correlation between production and average *C. lameensis* adults index on the plots prospected

a : Plots of 8 to 20 years old, b : Plots of 21 to 35 years old, c : Plots of 36 to 50 years old, d : Plots of 51 to 64 years old

Production losses by plots age

Over the 5 years of study (2015-2019), production losses were lower on the oldest plots (51 to 64 years old). Indeed, the losses recorded on these plots were on average 7130.2 bunches/year compared to 9277.4 bunches/year on plots from 8 to 20 years old, 9143.4 bunches/year on plots from 21 to 35 years old and 11330.6 bunches/year on plots from 36 to 50 years old. However, statistical analysis did not reveal significant differences in production losses between plots ($P > 0.05$) (Table 1).

Table 1 : Average production losses as a function of plots age

Age ranges of plots	Production losses/year
8 to 20 years old	9277.4 a
21 to 35 years old	9143.4 a
36 to 50 years old	11330.6 a
51 to 64 years old	7130.2 a

Averages belong to the same homogeneous group

Global level of *C. lameensis* and production depending on the plots

After 5 years of observation on the evolution of the population level of *C. lameensis* and production, it appears that the average index of *C. lameensis* larvae was higher on plots of 8 to 20 years old with 2.02 ± 0.97 larvae/palm against 1.43 ± 0.97 larva/palm on plots of 21 to 35 years, 0.28 ± 0.21 larva/palm on plots of 36 to 50 years and 0.64 ± 0.4 larva/palm on plots 51 to 64 years old. A significant variation in the mean index of larvae when moving from one category of plot to another ($P < 0.05$). However, the mean index of larvae of the 36 to 50 years old plots and that of the 50 to 64 years old plots were statistically identical and therefore the highest (Table 2).

Concerning the average index of *C. lameensis* adults, it was 2.27 ± 1.34 adult/palm on plots of 8 to 20 years old, 2 ± 1.42 adult/palm on plots of 21 to 36 years old, 0.55 ± 0.47 adult/palm on plots from 36 to 50 years old and 0.71 ± 0.42 adult/palm on plots from 50 to 64 years old. Significant differences were observed between the mean index of adults of the different plots ($P < 0.05$). However, the average index of *C. lameensis* adults recorded on the 8 to 20 years old plots and that recorded on the 21 to 35 years old plots were statistically identical and therefore the highest (Table 2).

As for the production, we harvest on average, 32881.2 ± 20307.24 bunches/year on plots of 8 to 20 years old, 29735.4 ± 844.16 bunches/year on plots of 21 to 35 years old, 20593 ± 13638.4 bunches/year on plots from 36 to 50 years old and 16650.4 ± 11546.3 bunches/year on plots from 51 to 64 years old. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed between the average number of bunches harvested/year depending on the plots. Thus, production was statistically higher on the youngest plots (8 to 20 years old). Likewise, it was statistically lower on the oldest plots (51 to 64 years) (Table 2).

Tableau 2 : Average index of *C. lameensis* and average bunches harvested according to plots for period 2015-2019

Age ranges of plots	Average index of larvae	Average index of adults	Average bunches harvested/year
8 to 20 years old	2.02 ± 0.97 a	2.27 ± 1.34 a	32881.2 ± 20307.4 a
21 to 35 years old	1.43 ± 0.97 b	2 ± 1.42 a	29735.4 ± 19844.16 b
36 to 50 years old	0.28 ± 0.21 c	0.55 ± 0.47 b	20593 ± 13638.4 c
51 to 64 years old	0.64 ± 0.4 c	0.71 ± 0.42 b	16650.4 ± 115463 d

Averages followed by the same letter in the same column are not statistically different at the 5% threshold.

DISCUSSION

October 31, 2021

The study showed that as the population level of *C. lameensis* increases, production is reduced and inversely. This development was observed on all categories of plots. Strong negative correlations were observed between the population level of *C. lameensis* and production at the level of all the plots surveyed. Thus, the decrease in production following an increase in the population level of *C. lameensis* could be explained by a strong defoliation of palms linked to the development of this pest. Indeed, the leaves constitute the part of the plant where photosynthesis takes place which is the starting point for the development of any chlorophyll plant (Benabdallah *et al.*, 2016; Rhoul, 2017). A strong defoliation of the plant could therefore prevent the good progress of photosynthesis and cause a loss of production.

The decrease in production resulting from the increase in the population level of *C. lameensis* is also linked to a deficiency or an excess of certain major mineral elements of the plant (nitrogen and chlorine). Jacquemard (1995), had indicated that excess nitrogen can depress production and thereby increase the susceptibility of the plant to certain pests and diseases. Likewise, chlorine is involved in the resistance of the plant to insect attacks and disease. Thus, on each of the categories of plots, the periods when the population level of *C. lameensis* increases would certainly be linked to an excess of nitrogen and/or a lack of chlorine in the palms. This would have made them vulnerable to the attacks of this pest. Hence the drop in production.

Overall, the population level of *C. lameensis* varied significantly from the youngest to the oldest plots. Indeed, this population level was higher on the youngest plots. It could be considered as a factor depending on the age of the plots as reported by Kouassi *et al.* (2019). These authors have shown that the population level of *C. lameensis* is lower on the youngest plot (4 years) and higher on the oldest plot (12 years). Allou *et al.* (2006), indicated that the oecophylls stand is very variable depending on the age of the coconut plots. Indeed, a high abundance of oecophylls was observed on plots of coconut palms over 4 years old. Ondo Ovono *et al.* (2014) reported that the presence of Rice Hemiptera Cicadellidae (stem borers) and the extent of damage they cause varies with the age of the rice plants. Indeed, their presence on rice begins at the tillering stage and continues until ripening with a peak at the heading stage and their population decreases at the ripening stage. They appreciate more the young reproductive organs (ears and flowers). In cashew trees, the parasitic infection of the plants progresses with the age of the plot and the oldest orchards (20 to 25 years), have the highest infection rate (more than 15%) (Soro *et al.*, 2020).

Production has gradually declined, moving from the oldest (young) plots to the oldest plots. Indeed, production was higher on the youngest plots (8 to 20 years old) and lower on the oldest plots (51 to 64 years old). The maximum production of oil palm is between 6 and 20 years (SOCFIN, 2016). Our results reflect this well since the age of the youngest plots (8 to 20 years old) is well within this age range. Rioualec (2012) had shown that oil palm production increases up to around 8 years with a maximum of 21 tonnes of bunches/ha/year, then stabilizes at 18 tonnes of bunches/ha/year up to 18 years before decreasing from the age of 20 up to 25 years when production drops to nearly 12 tonnes. The work of Aboubakar (2013), showed that oil palm production increases with the age of palm groves (from 1 to 21 years). In fact, production is zero during the juvenile growth phase (first three years), then it begins to grow from the age of 4 and stabilizes around 12 until the age of 21.

Despite the fact that the overall population level of *C. lameensis* was the highest (2 insects/ palm) on the youngest plots (8 to 20 years old), production was also the highest there. This could assume that this observed level of *C. lameensis* is not high enough to weaken production. This is justified since it is below the threshold of harmfulness (5 insects/palm). Likewise, if *C. lameensis* were not present or were at a lower level than that recorded on these plots, the recorded production would be even higher.

C. lameensis outbreaks are generally observed on plots older than 4 years (Philippe, 1992; Kouassi *et al.*, 2019). The study showed that despite the fact that the oldest plots were over 4 years old, they were the ones with the lowest levels of *C. lameensis*. This supposes that the low production observed on these plots is linked to factors other than the presence of *C. lameensis*. Dufour *et al.* (1988), Quencez (1996) and Yao *et al.* (1995) reported that annual oil palm production is affected by water stress. Jacquemard (1995) indicated that the water supply of the oil palm influences its vegetative development and its production of bunches (need of 5 mm of water/day, or 350 liters/tree or about 50 m³/hectare) to maximum production. The low

October 31, 2021

production on plots of 51 to 64 years old would therefore be linked to insufficient water supply and the formation of a low number of male and/or female flowers and/or abortion of young inflorescences.

The low production observed on the oldest plots could also be explained by an insufficiency or an excess of certain major mineral elements in the palm trees. According to Jacquemard (1995), the insufficiency or excess of major mineral elements in the plant (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium and chlorine) can cause low production. The rate of femininity also plays an important role in the production of oil palm. According to Meunier *et al.* (1989) and Tano *et al.* (2019), the production of diets is positively correlated with the femininity rate (the sex ratio). Thus, the increase in the number of diets and the increase in the sex ratio is one of the major factors in the increase in production. A low rate of femininity on the oldest plots (51 to 64 years old) would therefore be the cause of the low production observed.

Production losses were lower on the oldest plots (51 to 64 years). This could be explained by the fact that in this age group the population level of *C. lameensis* is low. Likewise, palm trees produce less than on other categories of plots as indicated above.

CONCLUSION

The increase in the population of *C. lameensis* leads to a decrease in production and inversely. Monitoring of palm groves should be regular in order to avoid production losses. *C. lameensis* population and production decline with increasing plot age. This should be taken into account in the establishment of palm groves in order to better forecast the periods of decline and increase in production.

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DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors wish to declare that they have no conflicting interest.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

ACK participated in data collection, data analysis and writing of the manuscript. AAMA participated in document collection, writing, and editing the manuscript. NH conceived the study, participated in data collection, in writing of the manuscript. AHN participated in data collection. HK and KPK participated in writing and editing the manuscript.

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October 31, 2021

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October 31, 2021

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